

Authors: Dr Miranda Geelhoed, Professor Jill Robbie

The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to Scotland's fourth land use strategy (LUS4): consultation

This document provides a response to the consultation on Scotland's fourth land use strategy. The [consultation document](#) has combined the consultation paper and the draft fourth Land Use Strategy (LUS4) into a single document. We welcome the consultation's focus on integrated landscapes, which we believe are essential for resolving land use conflicts and supporting the achievement of a wide range of land use-related policy objectives and targets. However, the LUS4 should provide the overarching strategy for land use in Scotland, under which other documents such as the proposed Just Transition Plan for the land use and agricultural sector should sit. LUS4 presents a vital opportunity to create coherence in a fragmented area of law and policy and to provide strategic direction for managing land use conflicts and trade-offs fairly, including in relation to agricultural peatlands and keeping in mind the restricted capacity of the land. Yet significant work remains to ensure LUS4 delivers an integrated, well-supported framework for land use policy and financing.

SECTION 1: LAND USE IN SCOTLAND

Q1. Do you find Map Figure 1 to be a helpful representation of current land cover?

No

[...]

Q3. What sort of information about current land use would you find useful? (and how would you use it?)

Map Figure 1 is a useful starting point, but there are limitations to the extent a single-layer map on current land cover can inform strategic land use decisions. To support robust, evidence-based land use decisions, the following types of information that can be captured in multiple-layer maps would be helpful:

- **Data on soil composition**, particularly the presence of (deep) peat deposits, and peat depth, which information is crucial for identifying restoration priorities.
- **Data on land use and land capability**. Whilst recognising the limitations of land use data (notably the sector-specific nature of data, which may be at odds with a strategy that focuses on supporting more integrated landscapes) this data can still be helpful to inform decisions. We note that the map has

sought to integrate Land Capability for Agriculture (LCA) data which is vital for understanding potential land use conflicts. However, such data should be continuously updated to take account of climate change risks (e.g., flood risk and extremes of weather), subsidence and land degradation.

- **Data on land tenure and ownership.** Land use change, although shaped by regulatory and financial instruments and markets, is largely achieved through the actions of individual landowners and land managers. Understanding barriers and opportunities in land governance – including complex tenure arrangements involving agricultural and crofting tenancies and common grazings – in relation to the physical capacities of the land to support peatland restoration, is not only crucial to implement strategic land use decisions and enable land use change, but also to achieve a just transition.

It is noted that the RESPECT project is working on a **Peatland Triage Tool (PTT)**, which aims to integrate different data sets to help landholders make informed choices about peatland restoration and management.

Q4. Do you agree that these are the key areas that need to be delivered by Scotland's land?

No

Q5. Are there any important land uses that you feel are missing or underrepresented in this list?

The list defines 'areas' or demands that need to be delivered by Scotland's land as being synonymous to specific policies which are likely to change over time including due to future changes in Government, e.g., see reference to the [Vision for Agriculture \(2022\)](#) rather than the statutory objectives of the [Agriculture and Rural Communities \(Scotland\) Act 2024](#). Considering that LUS4 will cover 2026-2031, it would be better to identify key demands on land – now and possibly in the future – in a more adaptive manner and then see to what degree they are currently covered by existing policies, targets and statutory requirements.

Agriculture, forestry, peatlands, biodiversity, housing, and renewables are key areas but there are areas missing, and the areas that are listed are too narrowly understood. We flag:

- **Climate change mitigation** more broadly, including soil and nutrient management.
- **Climate change adaptation**, including flood-risk management.
- **Biodiversity** more broadly, beyond designated areas and OECMS and including healthy peatlands that can support thriving wildlife and biodiversity in accordance with the [Biodiversity Strategy](#).
- **Conservation of the historic environment**, designated or not, including recognition of peatlands as heritage assets that can inform and contextualise long-term restoration planning.
- **Community wealth building** and the development of local economic opportunities, beyond the specific land-based sectors that are listed.

It is also noted that the target to restore 250,000 hectares of peatlands by 2030 does not come from the [National Peatland Plan \(2015\)](#) as the draft LUS4 suggests, but from the [Climate Change Plan 2018](#), reiterated by the updated [CCP from 2020](#) and informed by modelling by the UK Climate Change Committee which recommended the 20,000 hectares/year figure.

The areas must also not be treated as a list of separate priorities. A successful strategy must develop an integrated and strategic approach that seeks to manage different land use demands and inevitable trade-offs, keeping in mind that the capacity of the land to simultaneously deliver on all policy priorities may be restricted. Crucially, the principles of a just transition (under the [Climate Change \(Scotland\) Act 2009](#), s 35C) and the delivery of community benefits must be embedded as a cross-cutting theme across all these areas.

Q6. How do you think data and mapping can evolve to better support our understanding of future land use and national ambitions—including the impacts, benefits, opportunities and trade-offs of change?

Data and mapping must evolve to become dynamic tools for integrated land use planning. This requires:

- **Integration of diverse datasets:** Mapping must combine accessible physical data (e.g., soil cover and composition, land use and capacity, paleoenvironmental data, climate projections) with regulatory

data (e.g., tenure, historic and environmental designations, scope of agricultural payment schemes such as LFASS) and social data. This provides a holistic view needed to understand complex restrictions, trade-offs and opportunities.

- **Investment in data accessibility and longevity, particularly relating to historic data:** Data that may seem to be far-removed from tackling current challenges, at least from the perspective of landmanagers (e.g., ancient pollen), is essential to address contemporary and future land-based challenges. So much of our understanding of the development of landscapes and land-use over millennia is based on this data. However, as techniques to interrogate this data advance, enabling potentially significant contributions to be made to the design and planning of increasingly urgent interventions, there is a lack of strategic design in collating and making it accessible in the same way as contemporary data. Public investment is needed to digitise this information and ensure datasets are maintained and accessible long after research projects end. The importance of metadata also needs to be emphasised. Clear details of collection criteria, modelling (if any) and uncertainties, and the use of clear language (for example, definitions of peat) are vital for meaningful application of datasets to meet contemporary challenges.

Q7. What tools, data, or approaches would help improve this understanding over time?

As explained above, there needs to be much better recognition of the importance of historic environmental data for addressing contemporary and future land-based challenges. Recognising this puts into focus the need to ensure that such data is properly collated, stored and made accessible, which requires investment.

Elsewhere in this consultation response it is also noted that there are currently decisions being made that already have significant long-term impacts including in the way that they may limit the decision-making power, and the ability to adapt, of future landholders. For example, restoration projects under the Peatland Code involve contractual commitments of a minimum of 30 years, but an average of 80 years. The effectiveness and credibility of restoration projects, particularly where there is reliance on private finance, is reliant on robust (and publicly funded) mechanisms for monitoring, reporting and verification of benefits, which data should be collected and used to inform future approaches to undertake and finance restoration. Strong transparency in natural capital markets is needed to understand the implications for land governance. Also, having the right data available and accessible to inform decisions with very long-term impacts is a matter of urgency.

In this regard, the RESPECT project is developing a Peatland Triage Tool (PTT) to combine physical and social data to model the outcomes of different land use decisions and help users navigate and informed decisions about land use and land use change. A field to landscape approach will allow for scaling up, to incorporate data into regional based models and inform peatland restoration decisions at the national level.

SECTION 2: INTEGRATED LAND USE

Q8. Do you think the description provided captures what is meant by 'integrated landscapes'?

Yes

Q9. Do you agree that integrated landscapes are the most effective approach to addressing Scotland's land use ambitions?

Yes

We believe in a place-based approach to developing integrated and multifunctional landscapes that aim to resolve land use conflicts and deliver for Scotland's land use (change) ambitions, for example, relating to climate, biodiversity, food production and community wealth building.

Integrated landscapes can be more resilient – both in terms of ecological resilience (e.g., to impacts of climate change) and economic resilience (e.g., diverse income streams and spreading of risks). When adequately supported, they could also be key to a just transition, through more intentional design of policies that are inclusive of smaller farmers, tenants, crofters, and communities, ensuring benefits are shared more fairly.

Q10. Have we identified the right factors influencing land use integration?

No

Q11. Which of these factors do you feel are the most influential?

The most influential factor is a lack of a coherent and integrated overarching policy and financial framework to allow for a more strategic approach which is not listed as a key factor (see Q12).

Q12. Are there any important factors we have missed?

The factors identified are relevant, but the framework is incomplete and puts significant focus on the motivations, education and responsibilities of individual land managers. Integrated landscapes are essential to addressing Scotland's land use objectives, but they are not going to be realised without significant changes in policy – with the next LUS4 having the potential to deliver a much more strategic and integrated approach.

Current landscapes are often [compartmentalised](#) – they deliver primary benefits and purposes as (historically) incentivised by policies and financial instruments, with secondary benefits often under-valued and undersupported. Historically, law and policy, including public financial instruments, systematically drove the improvement of agricultural peatlands through drainage and intensification to boost production. Reversing this legacy and recognising peatlands as part of integrated and multifunctional landscapes – recognising notably their importance for climate and nature – is a central challenge. However, progress is hindered by the fact that peatlands currently sit in a very fragmented area of law and policymaking, with a lack of clarity and conflicts at strategic level (e.g., between climate/nature and food production) and at the implementation level (e.g., between funding streams, where agricultural payments can create disincentives for peatland restoration). At strategic level, it should be the LUS4 that sets out an integrated strategy for land use (change) in Scotland.

Additionally, the factors do include finance but mask just how important this factor is. There is an increasing emphasis in Scotland on unregulated markets to deliver public goods through land use (change), but natural capital markets barely get a mention in this consultation. It is not clear how reliance on private investors ([handling over power to make land use decisions over very long periods](#), even impacting future generations, e.g., the average project duration under the Peatland Code is more than 80 years) is going to help achieve more integrated landscapes and a more strategic approach to land use (change) in Scotland. This is a question that the next LUS should address head-on, providing adequate strategic direction to Scotland's land use future and guiding the development of policy and financial approaches to support land use change.

Lastly, a key factor that impacts on delivering integrated landscapes in an inclusive and just manner is Scotland's unusually concentrated pattern of rural landownership. Where integrated landscapes require collaboration – across ownership boundaries, or between landowners and crofters, tenants and communities – there is insufficient public funding for transaction costs and capacity building. The consultation document mentions Regional Land Use Partnerships, but [others such as Scottish Environment LINK have noted](#) how these Partnerships have been under-supported and are lacking powers, for example, to distribute funding to deliver on regional priorities following advice of the [Scottish Land Commission](#). Land reform and more research into, and support for, [collaborative land governance](#) is not separate from delivering an integrated land use strategy—it is a prerequisite for achieving it in a fair and just way.

Q13. Would the inclusion of case studies help to illustrate the practical delivery of integrated land use?

Yes

Q14. Would the inclusion of information on ecosystem services and opportunities for increased benefits help to illustrate the wider value of integrated landscapes?

Yes

SECTION 3: ROLE OF THE STRATEGY

Q15. Do you agree that the role of LUS4 should be to influence policy makers and regulators in order to create an enabling environment that incentivises and/or supports land managers, communities and partnerships to further integrate land use/management?

Yes

Q16. Are there other ways in which LUS4 could support alignment and integration?

Recognising LUS4 as the key strategy on land use (change) in Scotland, which provides direction on how trade-offs between different land use demands will be managed. In our response to the proposed Just Transition Plan for the land use and agriculture sector we have emphasised how LUS4 should set out the objectives for land use (change), with the LAJTP as a sub-set of the LUS4 which details how transitions in the land use and agricultural sectors will be managed in a *just* way, with concrete proposals. This means that LUS4 should not simply reference or copy-paste objectives from other strategies, but it should bring different laws and policies together and evaluate opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. In particular, we consider the need to integrate LUS4 with the anticipated Climate Change Plan, the Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Act 2024, the Land Reform Bill, the Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital, the Draft Just Transition Plan for the agriculture and land use sectors and the Biodiversity Strategy (and a future Natural Environment Bill).

Clearer responsibilities and greater political and financial support. It needs to be much clearer what the responsibilities of different departments of Scottish Government will be to implement the new LUS4. A new strategy will not be effective if it lacks awareness, political willingness and resources to support implementation. However, where appropriate governance mechanisms in support of a cross-sectoral strategy like LUS4 are put in place, they could allow for more coordinated, complementary and non-duplicative efforts across departments. This could lead to more resource-efficient implementation of land use change through policy and the allocation of public funds in such a way that delivers multiple policy objectives.

Championing and strengthening strategic approaches to land use at regional and local levels. There is a need for a much more integrated and strategic approach to land use policy and finance at national level, but the same applies to the regional and local level. LUS4 needs to bring together initiatives at all levels – including Regional Land Use Partnerships and Regional Land Use Frameworks (e.g., see [South of Scotland](#)) as well as more local Land Management Plans for large estates under a future Land Reform Act (where the LUS4 should inform the drafting of guidance on the content of such plans).

Q17. Do you agree with the proposed approach to developing a new vision and integrated set of objectives for the Land Use Strategy?

No

There should have been a possibility under Q17 to add an explanation, but there is not, so we have added this in our online response under Q18.

We believe that the economic framing risks narrowing Scotland's land use future and we propose the following vision instead: "Scotland's national landscape is integrated and resilient,—supporting the diverse needs of a net zero, nature-positive, wellbeing *nation*."

In relation to the themes and objectives, the document seeks to integrate, word-for-word, relevant objectives from other land use-related policies. Yet, the JHI [research](#) cited by the document highlighted that whilst there are already many explicit references between different relevant policies, there is "less evidence of the policies contributing to a transformation through systemically considering a range of land use goals". There is a real opportunity for the LUS4 to address this gap in policy integration to deliver effective coherence – including by evaluating the many different relevant policy objectives and providing strategic direction to resolve conflict between goals and measures, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land – but there is little evidence in the document that LUS4 will do this.

Q18. Which approach would you prefer for LUS4? Removal of the land use principles or establishment of a refreshed set of principles (if this is your preference, please tell us what you think they should cover and how you envision their application)?

Establishment of a refreshed set of principles

The current principles should be refreshed and significantly narrowed down, based on the LUS4 key objectives for land use (change) in Scotland. As stated elsewhere in our response, this document should provide clear strategic direction including objectives that bring different land use-related policies together. The LUS4 priorities and objectives (currently lacking) should inform a refreshed set of principles, which should also consider key principles of equity and justice following from:

- [Scottish Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement](#) (this was explicitly integrated into LUS3)
- [Statutory just transition principles](#)
- Community wealth building – [five pillars](#)

SECTION 4: MONITORING AND EVALUATING INTEGRATED, RESILIENT, AND SUSTAINABLE LAND USE

Q19. To what extent do you agree that the draft indicators provide a strong basis for measuring progress toward improved outcomes under the Nature and Climate theme?

Strongly Disagree

See above Q18. It is unclear what the actual objectives and proposed outcomes of LUS4 are, as the different themes just reference, word-for-word, the objectives included in other (draft) policies. Without knowing what the “improved outcomes” are, it is not possible to design indicators for success. We believe that LUS4 should set out the objectives and outcomes for land use (change) in Scotland, bringing different laws and policies together and evaluating opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. Success should be measured against these concrete proposed outcomes.

Where the improved outcome is “to progress towards more integrated landscapes” (p 29) it is very unclear how simple, quantitative metrics taken from other policies will help measure success. “Hectares of restored peatland” is an inadequate and potentially misleading indicator of success as it obscures crucial details about the quality of restoration, the delivery of multiple benefits including climate and biodiversity, and the social impacts at a local level. It is also unclear how it provides evidence of integrated landscapes. Where the outcomes are the objectives from other policies listed on p. 26, it is again unclear how “hectares of restored peatland” is an indicator of success of an aim like “natural capital / nature-based solutions projects not only help meet climate change and biodiversity targets but deliver value and opportunities for local communities” or “ecosystems will be diverse, healthy, resilient and deliver a wide range of ecosystem services”.

Q20. Are you aware of other data sources that could be used to monitor progress towards these outcomes?

No

We are not clear what outcomes the consultation document refers to. We believe that LUS4 should set out the objectives and outcomes for land use (change) in Scotland, bringing different laws and policies together and evaluating opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. Success should be measured against these concrete proposed outcomes.

Q21. To what extent do you agree that the draft indicators provide a strong basis for measuring progress toward improved outcomes under the Jobs, Skills and Economy theme?

Disagree

See above Q18. It is currently unclear what the actual objectives and proposed outcomes of LUS4 are, as the different themes just reference, word-for-word, the objectives included in other (draft) policies. Without knowing what the "improved outcomes" are, it is not possible to design indicators for success.

We believe that LUS4 should set out the objectives and outcomes for land use (change) in Scotland, bringing different laws and policies together and evaluating opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. Success should be measured against these concrete proposed outcomes.

Q22. Are you aware of other data sources that could be used to monitor progress towards these outcomes?**No**

We are not clear what outcomes the consultation document refers to. We believe that LUS4 should set out the objectives and outcomes for land use (change) in Scotland, bringing different laws and policies together and evaluating opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. Success should be measured against these concrete proposed outcomes.

Q23. To what extent do you agree that the draft indicators provide a strong basis for measuring progress toward improved outcomes under the Community, Places, People and Equity theme?**Strongly Disagree**

See above Q18. It is currently unclear what the actual objectives and proposed outcomes of LUS4 are, as the different themes just reference, word-for-word, the objectives included in other (draft) policies. Without knowing what the "improved outcomes" are, it is not possible to design indicators for success. We believe that LUS4 should set out the objectives and outcomes for land use (change) in Scotland, bringing different laws and policies together and evaluating opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. Success should be measured against these concrete proposed outcomes.

Where the improved outcome simply is "to progress towards more integrated landscapes" (p 29) it is very unclear how simple, quantitative metrics like "number of assets in community ownership" or "area of land in community ownership" is a measure of success for achieving this outcome.

Q24. Are you aware of other data sources that could be used to monitor progress towards these outcomes?**No**

We are not clear what outcomes the consultation document refers to. We believe that LUS4 should set out the objectives and outcomes for land use (change) in Scotland, bringing different laws and policies together and evaluating opportunities for synergies and conflicts between aims and targets, keeping in mind the restricted capacities of the land. Success should be measured against these concrete proposed outcomes.

SECTION 5: ASSESSING IMPACT**Q25. Are you aware of any ways in which the proposed vision and objectives need to consider the different experiences, both positive and negative, current or future, of the following groups (island communities, young people, those with protected characteristics, groups or areas at socio-economic disadvantage)?**

Yes, although it is noted again that it is not clear what the actual objectives of LUS4 will be.

A just transition requires that the LUS4 vision and objectives are designed to intentionally address inequities in power and distribution of risks and benefits.

- **Young people:** The vision must acknowledge the long-term nature of land use change. Decisions made now on carbon projects can lock up land for 80+ years, so (governance) mechanisms are needed to represent the interests of current and future generations.
- **Areas at socio-economic disadvantage:** Many rural areas already face structural inequalities, including limited access to services, out-migration of young people, and reliance on low-margin agricultural livelihoods. The expansion of natural capital markets risks exacerbating these divides if wealth generated through carbon and biodiversity credits benefits mainly those that control large areas of natural resources, large landowners or external investors. Objectives must therefore commit to ensuring that financial and non-financial benefits from land use change are retained locally, and that investment does not drive further concentration of landownership or rural depopulation.
- **Groups at socio-economic disadvantage,** which could be interpreted to include tenants, crofters, and small farmers. These groups can face significant barriers, including:
 - o Lack of capacity and high transaction costs to engage with complex funding schemes.
 - o Insecure land tenure and the need for landowner consent, which can prevent them from participating in a just transition towards net zero through land use (change).
 - o Being outcompeted in a land market driven by private investors.

Q26. Are you aware of any potential costs and burdens that you think may arise as a result of the vision and objectives within this consultation?

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